

DMP for the LZP FLPP project - "Study of health literacy in Latvia: levels, burden and interventions" (HeLiL, Izp-2024/1-0543)

Version 1

Description

This document represents the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the research study (2025–2027) conducted under the Fundamental and Applied Research Grants funded by Latvian Council of Science, project "Study of health literacy in Latvia: levels, burden and interventions" (HeLiL, Izp-2024/1-0543). The DMP will be managed as a living document using the Argos DMP tool, with significant updates periodically uploaded to Zenodo throughout the project's duration. Regular revisions will align with periodic project evaluations, or more frequently as necessary.

The DMP provides a comprehensive strategy for managing data generated during the HeLiL project. The project's primary aim is to advance knowledge and scholarly discussions regarding health literacy by assessing the current status of health literacy in Latvia, estimating the impact of low levels of health literacy, and identifying cost-effective interventions to enhance health literacy skills. This plan outlines procedures for data handling, storage, sharing, and preservation, ensuring alignment with the project's objectives and facilitating future research and development.

The HeLiL project employs a mixed-method research design, integrating qualitative and quantitative data collection methods to achieve its goals. Data generation and collection will strictly adhere to European Union and national ethical and legal standards. Specifically, data will be collected through comprehensive scientific literature reviews, qualitative methods (interviews and group discussions), and quantitative methods (original survey questionnaires).

The final research outputs will also include a policy report outlining evidence-based, context-sensitive methods, tools, and interventions designed to promote health literacy in Latvia.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research Programme (FLPP)

Researchers

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Organizations

Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP for the LZP FLPP project - "Study of health literacy in Latvia: levels, burden and interventions" (HeLiL, Izp-2024/1-0543)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Fundamental and Applied Research Programme (FLPP)

Project: lzp-2024/1-0543

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

A survey dataset regarding health literacy of adult population in Latvia

The survey will include a high-quality, representative sample (n=2007) of the adult Latvian population. It will generate a comprehensive database demographically representative of Latvians aged 18–75, containing a wide range of metrics essential for assessing the burden of low health literacy and developing actionable interventions to improve health literacy outcomes.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

A representative survey is planned to be conducted in 2025 and its purpose is to uncover the complex interrelations between health literacy levels, health behaviours, and the use of healthcare resources.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

SAV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered reusing any existing data because no such data is available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers, health services providers, policy makers, governmental institutions, students etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period will be applied until scientific articles are submitted for publication and published as well as the final project assessment is finalised (i.e., till the end of 2029).

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv>

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for long-term preservation and publication of research data.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Creative Commons is a nonprofit organization that provides open licenses and legal tools to help researchers share their work. The license mandates that users give proper credit to the creator and permits them to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the content in any medium or format.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2031-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2131-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

All personnel expenses will be covered within the project "Study of health literacy in Latvia: levels, burden and interventions" (HeLiL, Izp-2024/1-0543).

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Ágnes Lubloy (0000-0002-3701-1876)
- Marija Krumina (0009-0006-7890-6445)
- Lelde Jakobsonsone

Project leader Ágnes Lubláy and researcher Marija Krūmiņa will handle the data description and processing. Research administrator Lelde Jakobsonsone will oversee the process and ensure it aligns with other activities while providing guidance.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The costs of making the data available via a repository are limited to the time researchers may need to prepare the data for archiving, so it's recommended to plan for this early while the project is still ongoing. Therefore costs will be covered within the project "Study of health literacy in Latvia: levels, burden and interventions" (HeLiL, Izp-2024/1-0543).

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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